

The ENEA TRIGA RC-1 reactor within the SECURE Project: key aspects of a potential ^{161}Tb production cycle

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20804020

ABSTRACT

The European project SECURE aimed to strengthen the resilience and autonomy of the European medical radioisotope supply chain, addressing current dependencies on non-European production and the progressive aging of reactor infrastructure. Within this framework, ENEA investigated the production of terbium-161 (^{161}Tb), a promising radionuclide for targeted radionuclide therapy (TRT) due to its favorable decay properties and chemical compatibility with lutetium-177 (^{177}Lu). This study assesses the feasibility of ^{161}Tb production at the ENEA TRIGA RC-1 reactor through neutron irradiation of ^{160}Gd -enriched gadolinium oxide (Gd_2O_3) targets. Monte Carlo simulations were performed to evaluate neutron flux distribution, self-shielding effects, and the reactivity impact of increasing target masses.

Within SECURE, the ENEA TRIGA RC-1 team assessed the feasibility of local radionuclide production in Italy via neutron activation of Gd_2O_3 targets highly enriched (>98%) in ^{160}Gd . After chemical processing, ^{161}Tb is extracted and purified for medical supply, while ^{160}Gd oxide is recovered and reused in subsequent irradiation cycles.

In view of a potential scale-up, different irradiation configurations containing significant quantities of Gd_2O_3 were analysed to quantify (i) achievable ^{161}Tb activity, (ii) neutron self-shielding, and (iii) reactivity insertion, with the goal of identifying an efficient and operationally safe setup.

Keywords: TRIGA reactor, terbium-161, neutron activation technique, medical isotopes.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the decommissioning of major nuclear facilities dedicated to medical radionuclide production has posed significant challenges to diagnostic imaging and radiotherapy, highlighting vulnerabilities of the current supply chain and causing intermittent shortages of essential medical radioisotopes, such as molybdenum-99/technetium-99m, and several therapeutic β -emitters [1, 2].

In response, worldwide R&D efforts have been launched to identify more resilient sources of supply and alternative production routes, aiming to ensure continuity of nuclear-medicine applications while strengthening national and European self-sufficiency and reducing the risk of disruptions [3, 4].

With this objective, the ENEA TRIGA RC-1 reactor joined the EU-funded SECURE Project (HORIZON-EURATOM-2021-NRT-01 call, Strengthening the European Chain of sUpply for next generation medical RadionuclidEs, October 2022–September 2025) [5]. The project aimed to contribute to the long-term sustainability of medical radioisotope production and supply in Europe, ensuring stable availability for

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diagnostic and therapeutic use. It focused on innovative radionuclides, new irradiation-target designs, and novel production routes for both established and emerging radioisotopes.

One of the radionuclides investigated in SECURE was ^{161}Tb , a promising candidate for cancer treatment, showing similar decay characteristics and chemical behaviour to the clinically employed ^{177}Lu . A typical lutetium therapy involves six injections of 6 GBq at six-week intervals; analogous protocols with terbium are expected to require administered activities of the same order of magnitude, despite the higher therapeutic efficacy of ^{161}Tb . Therapeutic effects of ^{161}Tb are enhanced due to the co-emission of a larger number of conversion and Auger electrons, which are more effective in the treatment of micrometastases and single cancer cells [6, 7].

The ENEA Casaccia Research Centre contributed to the project by focusing on ^{161}Tb production within TRIGA RC-1. This is obtained by neutron activation of a gadolinium target, highly enriched (over 98%) in ^{160}Gd , to overcome limitations in chemical and radiochemical purity typically observed in the final product. Enrichment also facilitates chemical processing, which involves extraction and purification of both ^{161}Tb —the radionuclide precursor for radiopharmaceutical preparation—and ^{160}Gd oxide, which can be recovered and reused in subsequent irradiation cycles (fundamental to contain overall costs, since enriched target material is the most expensive item).

The proposed scheme requires irradiation of relatively large quantities of raw material, because research reactors operating at medium-to-low neutron flux generally achieve lower activity concentrations than dedicated production reactors. Consequently, tens to hundreds of grams may be needed in the former case, whereas fractions of a gram can be sufficient in production reactors.

Given the limited activity concentration achievable at a 1 MW_{th} TRIGA reactor, economic sustainability is expected to be driven by: (i) irradiated ^{160}Gd mass, (ii) produced ^{161}Tb activity, (iii) enriched-material cost, (iv) selling price of ^{161}Tb , and (v) efficiency of separation, purification, and recycling. A dedicated cost discussion is included in [8].

This paper presents the main neutronic and operational constraints for a potential ^{161}Tb production cycle at ENEA TRIGA RC-1. Monte Carlo simulations and deterministic calculations were performed to evaluate (i) neutron self-shielding in massive Gd_2O_3 targets, (ii) reactivity insertion as a function of target mass and axial positioning, and (iii) possible irradiation-channel modifications aimed at increasing the thermal neutron component and the final production.

2. METHODOLOGY

Neutron Activation Analysis (NAA) is a method of quantitative chemical analysis based on the nuclear activation of chemical elements present in a sample. While primarily used for trace-element quantification, neutron activation can also be exploited for radionuclide production, where the goal is to maximise yield under facility constraints.

The TRIGA RC-1 is a medium-scale research reactor (1 MW_{th}), with a neutron fluence rate on the order of $1 \times 10^{13} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. This differs from established production reactors (typically operating at $\sim 10^{14} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and higher), with direct consequences on the achievable activity concentration in the target material.

From a technical point of view, the reaction chain $^{160}\text{Gd}(n,\gamma)^{161}\text{Gd}(\beta^-)^{161}\text{Tb}$ does not exhibit a particularly favourable microscopic cross section in the thermal region ($\sigma_0=1.4 \text{ b}$ at 0.0253 eV [9]). To increase the final activity of ^{161}Tb , optimisation of irradiation conditions and target characteristics is required (chemical form, mass, composition, irradiation position, and irradiation schedule).

Regarding target characteristics, within ENEA TRIGA RC-1 irradiation of liquid samples is avoided (except under specific conditions and reduced volumes). Solid targets are therefore preferred, enabling irradiation of masses up to a few hundred grams to compensate for the lower neutron fluence rate.

Table I. Isotopic abundance of enriched Gd_2O_3 target material; natural abundances are also reported for reference.

Isotope	^{152}Gd	^{154}Gd	^{155}Gd	^{156}Gd	^{157}Gd	^{158}Gd	^{160}Gd
enriched isotopic abundance wt. [%]	<0.01	0.01	0.18	0.36	0.25	1	98.2 (± 0.1)
natural isotopic abundance wt. [%]	0.19	2.13	14.6	20.3	15.6	24.9	22.2

Finally, high enrichment in ^{160}Gd is necessary to achieve higher yields and to reduce neutron self-shielding from other Gd isotopes, since gadolinium is a strong burnable neutron poison. Accordingly, the selected target material is Gd_2O_3 powder, with the enriched isotopic distribution reported in Table I.

With respect to irradiation conditions, the target must be placed at the point of maximum neutron flux, i.e. the Central Thimble (approximately $5 \times 10^{13} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 1 MW_{th}) [10]. The irradiation time should ideally span at least 1.5–3 half-lives of ^{161}Tb (10–20 days of continuous irradiation) to ensure adequate utilisation of the enriched batch; under ideal conditions, saturation would be reached after roughly 30 days.

However, such extended irradiation is not feasible at ENEA TRIGA RC-1 for two main reasons:

- operational constraints, including a maximum irradiation time of 6 hours per day;
- the reactor core may require optimisation of excess reactivity management when irradiating large amounts of neutron-absorbing material.

The irradiation schedule considered by TRIGA RC-1 staff involves placing the sample in the Central Thimble for 12 days, with 6–7 hours per day, excluding Saturdays and Sundays, for a total of approximately 72–84 hours.

This discontinuous schedule introduces relevant ^{161}Tb decay losses between irradiation days. The campaign includes 11 overnight and 2 weekend interruptions (13 waiting periods, ~ 280 hours of decay), reducing EOI activity by about 80% compared with ideal continuous irradiation over the same 15-day period. Therefore, relaxing operational constraints and enabling continuous irradiation would significantly increase ^{161}Tb yield.

The final activity of ^{161}Tb (A) at the end of irradiation can be estimated as $A=R(1-e^{-\lambda t_{irr}})$, where t_{irr} is the irradiation time (s), λ is the decay constant (s^{-1}), and R is the reaction rate:

$$R = N_t \int \sigma(E) \phi(E) dE = N_t [G_{th} \phi_0 \sigma_0 g + \phi_e (G_{res} I_0 + f)] \quad (1)$$

In Equation (1), N_t is the number of atoms of the parent nuclide in the sample, $\sigma(E)$ is the microscopic cross section, and $\phi(E)$ is the neutron flux. In the ASTM E262-08/97 formulation, ϕ_0 and ϕ_e are thermal and epithermal flux components, G_{th} and G_{res} are self-shielding factors, σ_0 and I_0 are the thermal cross section and resonance integral, and g and f are the Westcott and sub-cadmium epithermal correction factors.

The computational tools used for activity determination and inventory evolution are MCNPX v2.5.0 [11], ASTM E262-08 / ASTM E262-97 [12], and FISPACT-II [13]. ASTM E262-08/97 methodologies are also used for neutron characterisation of reactor channels.

FISPACT-II is a deterministic inventory and activation code used to model nuclide transmutation and decay under a prescribed neutron spectrum and irradiation schedule. In this work, FISPACT-II was not coupled with MCNP in the classical literature approach, because its self-shielding treatment for massive Gd samples is not reliable (often overestimating activities). Therefore, FISPACT-II results were mainly used for conservative radiation-protection and reactivity-evolution purposes.

Conversely, MCNP enables accurate modelling of complex geometries and detailed neutron transport, allowing reliable quantification of neutron self-shielding. Reaction rates can be computed directly, and

self-shielding correction factors can be derived consistently for ASTM E262-08/97. Two complementary approaches were adopted: (i) direct reaction-rate calculation using MCNPX F4/FM4 tallies; and (ii) the ASTM E262 estimator, where self-shielding factors are derived from MCNPX calculation and applied in the ASTM formulation.

Overall, these tools were used to perform preliminary calculations to assess the producible ^{161}Tb activity when irradiating large amounts of raw material in ENEA TRIGA RC-1 by:

1. quantifying neutron self-shielding and achievable activity for increasing target masses;
2. evaluating reactivity insertion to verify compliance with reactor constraints;
3. studying potential irradiation-channel modifications (e.g. intentional moderation by water filling) to enhance the thermal neutron component.

2.1. Irradiation of large target masses: self-shielding and reactivity constraints

Irradiating larger quantities of raw material enables reaching higher absolute activity.

To evaluate the maximum achievable activity, the TRIGA RC-1 standard aluminium capsule was simulated with the maximum amount of material that can be introduced, ~ 400 g of Gd_2O_3 .

For such massive samples, FISPACT-II is not realistic because it does not account adequately for neutron self-shielding. Conversely, MCNP allows calculation of self-shielding factors (G_{th} and G_{res}) and direct computation of reaction rates (Equation (1)), providing more accurate activity estimates.

A flux tally (F4) was defined in the sample region, and an FM4 multiplier was used to obtain reaction rate and, by applying the irradiation schedule, EOI activity. The MCNP material composition was based on a commercially available formulation including enriched Gd_2O_3 (Table I) and trace impurities.

The fully filled aluminium capsule was positioned with its bottom at the reactor core centre (Figure 2-(a)), so the bottom part experiences the highest flux, while the upper part is exposed to a lower ($\sim 40\%$) flux. In this configuration, the final activity achieved is about 690 GBq.

Axial positioning with the capsule mid-height at the core centre maximises activation (780 GBq), but induces a negative reactivity insertion of ~ -560 pcm, exceeding the -500 pcm operational limit for mobile experiments. This excess negative reactivity is due to the non-negligible presence of the highly absorbing isotopes ^{155}Gd and ^{157}Gd .

To respect reactor constraints, less massive samples and additional optimisation of the irradiation geometry were investigated. The compromise configuration corresponds to a 125 g sample placed in the same position, leading to a maximum negative reactivity insertion of ~ 440 pcm (Table III).

Different geometrical configurations of 125 g of Gd_2O_3 were studied to maximise ^{161}Tb activity while minimising self-shielding. Since irradiation commonly uses quartz tubes, two configurations were analysed: 4 vials (~ 31 g each) and 9 vials (~ 14 g each), placed inside the licensed aluminium capsule. Both configurations yield ~ 340 GBq at EOI (Table II).

Additionally, the 9-vials configuration was simulated in a channel filled with light water. Although moderation improves the spectrum (+40% thermal component; +10% energy-integrated flux, Figure 1), the gain is largely neutralised by self-shielding; the final ^{161}Tb production is 350 GBq (+3%) versus 340 GBq for the empty channel.

The reactivity evolution during irradiation was studied using FISPACT-II and MCNP in a complementary manner. FISPACT-II was employed to model sample composition evolution, accounting for all nuclides produced. FISPACT-II was used conservatively: due to its underestimation of self-shielding, depletion of key absorbers (^{155}Gd , ^{157}Gd) occurs faster than in reality, accelerating inventory evolution. This probes the maximum negative reactivity and verifies that the trend remains negative and monotonically decreasing. The step-by-step compositions were then implemented in MCNP to com-

pute time-dependent k_{eff} , confirming that reactivity remains within safe limits over the 12-day cycle (Table III).

2.2. Neutron flux for different Central Thimble configurations

In TRIGA RC-1, optimising the producible activity is essential. Therefore, for the 125 g case, simulations were performed by adding moderator material inside the irradiation channel.

The objective is to improve neutron thermalisation and increase the thermal flux component. Using MCNP, neutron flux values were calculated by dividing the spectrum into 56 energy groups. This choice was driven by computational constraints, requiring each calculation $\sim 32\,000$ h-core to achieve acceptable statistical uncertainties; the group structure is derived (by condensing) from the 66-group LANL structure reported in the FISPACT-II manual [13].

The flux was computed for three configurations:

1. the Central Thimble in empty configuration;
2. the Central Thimble filled with light water;
3. the Central Thimble filled with heavy water.

Figure 1. Neutron fluxes in different Central Thimble configurations.

The results are shown in Figure 1. The channel filled with light water shows the highest thermal flux. This increase by a factor ~ 1.5 can increase final activity for samples not strongly affected by self-shielding. However, for gadolinium targets the benefit is largely neutralised by strong absorption, so no significant variation in final activity is observed between dry and water-filled configurations for large samples (Table II).

3. RESULTS

The results obtained by simulating the maximum amount of material that can be loaded into the capsule are shown in Table II. Results obtained using MCNP and ASTM E262 methods are in good agreement.

The uncertainty values reported in Table II are strongly affected by the large uncertainties (17%–25% [9]) in the $^{160}\text{Gd}(n,\gamma)^{161}\text{Gd}(\beta^-)^{161}\text{Tb}$ nuclear data. For ASTM, dominant contributions arise from experimentally determined neutron fluence rate (7–13%, $k = 1$) and nuclear data; for MCNP, from reactor source-strength scaling (about 10%, $k = 1$) and nuclear data. Combining contributions yields an overall uncertainty of 37–39% ($k = 1$), consistent with Table II when expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$) is reported.

In Table II, the 125 g cases lead to a higher activity concentration, indicating better utilisation of raw material compared to the 400 g configuration. Numerically, activity concentration increases from 2.01 GBq/g_{Gd-160} (400 g case) to ~ 3.2 GBq/g_{Gd-160} (125 g cases), mainly due to reduced self-shielding (G_{th} from 0.06 to 0.12) and improved neutron penetration in smaller vials.

Overall, as sample mass increases, activity concentration decreases even for enriched samples and optimised geometries. This is due to the presence of gadolinium isotopes: ^{155}Gd and ^{157}Gd , in particular, exhibit significantly higher absorption cross sections than ^{160}Gd .

The reactivity decrease in Table III is explained by depletion of the highly absorbing isotopes ^{155}Gd and ^{157}Gd . In view of raw-material reuse, their depletion increases self-shielding factors (G_{th} and G_{res}), enhancing effective ^{161}Tb production in subsequent cycles.

With this aim, additional simulations were performed. The increase of G_{th} is confirmed. Having as-

Table II. Results of ^{161}Tb activity obtained irradiating enriched Gd_2O_3 (98.2% ^{160}Gd) in different (a)...(d) configurations in Figure 2.

Configuration	Sample mass Gd_2O_3	Activity [GBq]	MCNP Act. conc. [$\text{GBq}/\text{g}_{\text{Gd}-160}$]	Activity [GBq]	ASTM Act. conc. [$\text{GBq}/\text{g}_{\text{Gd}-160}$]	G_{th}	G_{res}
(a) full capsule empty channel	400 g	$685 \pm 78\%$	2.01	$692 \pm 78\%$	2.07	0.06	0.31
(b) 4 vials empty channel	125 g	$337 \pm 78\%$	3.16	$337 \pm 78\%$	3.15	0.12	0.37
(c) 9 vials empty channel	125 g	$343 \pm 78\%$	3.22	$341 \pm 78\%$	3.20	0.12	0.37
(d) 9 vials water channel	125 g	$351 \pm 78\%$	3.29	–	–	0.09	0.38

Table III. Reactivity caused by the presence of Gd_2O_3 samples in different configurations during the irradiation period. ^{161}Tb production trend vs. time for the 12-days irradiation protocol, in the 4-vials case. Activity values are referred to irradiation day-12 as the reference date.

Geometry	Sample mass Gd_2O_3	day of irradiation	^{161}Tb activity [GBq]	k_{eff}	k_0	ρ	pcm
full capsule, empty channel, bottom of the capsule at the core centre	400 g	0	–	0.98976	0.99406	-4.34E-3	-434.45
full capsule, empty channel, mid-height of the capsule at the core centre	400 g	0	–	0.98851	0.99406	-5.61E-3	-561.45
4 vial, empty channel, mid-height of the capsule at the core centre	125 g	0	–	0.98968	0.99405	-4.42E-3	-441.56
	125 g	2	25	0.98970	0.99405	-4.40E-3	-439.53
	125 g	5	75	0.98977	0.99405	-4.32E-3	-432.42
	125 g	7	130	0.98981	0.99405	-4.28E-3	-428.37
	125 g	10	240	0.98991	0.99405	-4.18E-3	-418.22
	125 g	12	340	0.98997	0.99405	-4.12E-3	-412.13

sumed recycling of Gd oxide raw material, before starting the third irradiation cycle the sample shows $G_{th}=0.36$, compared to $G_{th}=0.12$ in the first use. This increase leads –considering the 125 4-vials configuration in Table II– to a final activity of 590 GBq of ^{161}Tb (compared to 337 GBq in the first cycle) and an activity concentration of $5.5 \text{ GBq}_{\text{Tb}-161} / \text{g}_{\text{Gd}-160}$ (compared to $3.2 \text{ GBq}_{\text{Tb}-161} / \text{g}_{\text{Gd}-160}$ in the first cycle).

This example shows that the reduction in atom density of ^{155}Gd and ^{157}Gd during irradiation has an increasingly significant impact on neutron self-shielding factors. Such effects must be carefully evaluated when designing the closed cycle for Gd oxide raw material to determine the maximum number of recycling batches allowed by chemical and radiochemical purity constraints of the final products.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This work investigated the feasibility of producing ^{161}Tb at the ENEA TRIGA RC-1 reactor using neutron activation techniques.

As previously emphasised, TRIGA RC-1 is a medium-scale research reactor and cannot produce radionuclide activities comparable to standard production reactors, mainly due to its lower neutron flux and operating schedule. Consequently, each step of the production cycle must be optimised to maximise efficiency.

The analyses indicate that limitations in achievable activity are not solely due to reduced neutron flux, but also to restrictions on irradiation volumes and to the limited operating schedule.

In this context, both the selection of the target material and its geometry become critical parameters. Gadolinium, being a strong neutron absorber, is inherently less suitable for irradiation compared to other target materials. Nevertheless, ^{160}Gd remains attractive for ^{161}Tb production because it provides a direct, no-carrier-added route to terbium, enabling high radionuclidic purity after chemical separation.

Experiments carried out, in particular the irradiation of 8.7 mg of Gd_2O_3 enriched to 98.2% in ^{160}Gd ,

Figure 2. Various configurations of $^{160}\text{Gd}_2\text{O}_3$ raw-material capsules in the MCNP code: (a) 400 g full capsule, bottom of the capsule at the core centre, empty channel; (b) 125 g 4-vials, empty channel; (c) 125 g 9-vials, empty channel; (d) 125 g 9-vials with Central Channel flooded with light water. All (b), (c) and (d) configurations have the mid-height position of the capsule corresponding to reactor core centre.

demonstrated a maximum production capacity of ENEA TRIGA RC-1 of 15 GBq per gram of ^{160}Gd under a 77-hour discontinuous irradiation cycle [16, 17].

For comparison, a similar 7.3 mg Gd_2O_3 (98.2% ^{160}Gd) was irradiated for 10 days continuously at ILL within a neutron flux of $10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The EOI ^{161}Tb activity achieved is ~ 17 GBq, corresponding to an activity concentration of ~ 2700 GBq per gram of ^{160}Gd [6]. This highlights the role of high neutron flux and continuous irradiation. Conversely, production at medium-to-low flux reactors requires larger raw-material masses and, where possible, continuous irradiation protocols.

Simulations assessed irradiation of larger masses. The maximum allowable configuration corresponds to ~ 125 g of Gd_2O_3 (98.2% ^{160}Gd) irradiated in the Central Thimble for 12 days, 6–7 hours per day excluding weekends (total 77 hours). This yields ~ 340 GBq, i.e. $\sim 3 \text{ GBq}_{\text{Tb-161}}/\text{g}_{\text{Gd-160}}$ for the first batch. Target recovery, purification, and depletion of ^{155}Gd and ^{157}Gd may significantly increase this concentration in subsequent recycling batches.

Considering only the first irradiation round, an initial activity of about 340 GBq is obtained. Accounting for about one week of extraction and chemical processing (roughly one ^{161}Tb half-life), the medically usable activity is estimated at ~ 170 GBq. Assuming a therapy scheme analogous to ^{177}Lu (six injections of 6 GBq at six-week intervals), this activity would be sufficient to treat around 30 patients per month.

With regard to feasibility of the entire production cycle, the ENEA team also addressed chemical processing and recycling of large quantities of enriched raw material, demonstrating technical viability. Economic assessments and life-cycle analysis indicate that the high cost of enriched Gd_2O_3 remains the main limiting factor for long-term sustainability [8]. Additional irradiation campaigns and chemical processing tests are planned to consolidate the current results and refine the workflow.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The publication was created within the project SECURE funded by the European Union under grant agreement No. 101061230.

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